

On the global buckling of steel sandwich panels

Kevin Janczyk^{*,a}, Jonas Nonn^b, Markus Kuhnhenne^a, Markus Feldmann^b

^aRWTH Aachen University, Institute of Steel Construction, Chair for Sustainable Metal Building Envelopes, Germany

^bRWTH Aachen University, Institute of Steel Construction, Chair for Steel and Lightweight Metal Construction,
Germany

kevin.janczyk@stb.rwth-aachen.de, jonas.nonn@stb.rwth-aachen.de, kuhnhenne@stb.rwth-aachen.de,
feldmann@stb.rwth-aachen.de

ABSTRACT

Sandwich panels are one of the market-leading systems for building envelopes in industrial and commercial construction. In this function, they are generally used as self-supporting elements. Thereby, they are subjected to wind and temperature loads. These external loads lead to bending stress on the panels. The sandwich panels absorb these loads and transfer them to the substructure. In other areas of application, such as cold room construction, sandwich panels are subjected to axial loads. Cold rooms for example can be realised entirely from sandwich panels without a substructure and without a primary supporting structure, so that the sandwich panels take on the load transfer of the entire structure. In this case, sandwich panels that are used as vertically installed wall elements are subjected to axial loads. For the axial loading of sandwich panels, a design concept based on stress analyses can be found in the draft of the new Eurocode 3 prEN 1993 7 "Design of steel structures - sandwich panels" (1). A design concept based on the geometric and structural imperfections is neither included in the literature nor in the draft of the new standard. This paper presents new investigations on the global buckling of sandwich panels. Thereby, the load-bearing behaviour is evaluated taking real imperfections of the panels into account. These imperfections are determined using the Southwell plot and compared with measured geometric imperfections. In addition, the Southwell plot is used to evaluate the analytical approaches. Finally, a method is presented which can be used in the future as a basis for the development of buckling curves of sandwich panels.

Keywords: Lightweight metal construction, sandwich panels, buckling, composite structures

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels are generally used as building envelopes in industrial and commercial construction. They usually consist of two steel faces and a core of mineral wool (MW), polyurethane (PUR) or polystyrene rigid foam (PIR). The core provides the thermal insulation function of these components. In addition to the classic application in the area of self-supporting building envelopes, there is an increasing demand for new sandwich constructions, which should be realised without any substructure. Thereby, the panels contribute to the overall stability of the building. This means that, as load-bearing wall elements, they are also subjected to axial loads. In this respect, they must transfer the loads from the roof of the building as well as the installations on it, such as building service installations.

The axially loaded sandwich panels can generally be considered as a axially loaded bar according to Euler case II. Accordingly, the global buckling of relatively slender panels represents the decisive case for design. The draft of the new standard prEN 1993-7 "Design of steel structures - sandwich panels" (1) contains a first verification concept for sandwich panels under axial loading.

A design concept based on tests in accordance with the European buckling curves would have the advantage that component-specific properties of the sandwich panels, such as the size of the structural

and geometric imperfections and the actual load-bearing capacity, could be directly taken into account.

This paper presents new investigations on the global buckling of sandwich panels under centric axial loads. A method which can be used in the future as a basis for the development of European buckling curves will be developed.

2 AXIALLY LOADED SANDWICH PANELS

Figure 1 shows the principle load bearing behaviour of the global buckling of sandwich panels. The load-deflection of an ideal sandwich panel under axially loading is shown in grey. Thereby, the load increases without any lateral deformation until the critical buckling load is reached. Then, global buckling occurs and the lateral deflection of the panel increases till the wrinkling stress of the face is reached. The so called wrinkling stress is the limit value of the stress acting in the compressively loaded face of the panel, which leads to a local stability failure of the face (2), (3), (4). The wrinkling of the face leads to the failure of the entire component.

The load bearing-behaviour of a real panel is presented in blue. Real sandwich panels do always have structural and geometrical imperfections. For this reason, lateral displacement occurs even at a low load level when an axial load is applied. The closer the applied force comes to the critical load, the greater the disproportionate increase in lateral deflection as a result of the second-order effects. The failure of the panel is then caused by reaching the wrinkling stress. Further theoretical descriptions can be found in (2), (5), (6), (7), (8), for example.

Fig. 1. Load-bearing behaviour of axially loaded sandwich panels

The deformation calculation of a sandwich panel must take into account the shear deformation of the core material. The additional shear deflection must therefore also be taken into account in the global buckling calculation of sandwich panels. An approach to extend the known formula for the critical buckling load N_{cr} by the shear modulus G_C was presented, for example, by Engesser in (9). Thereby, the critical buckling load for sandwich panels is calculated according to equation (1).

$$N_{cr,Engesser} = \frac{\frac{\pi^2 \cdot B_s}{L_{cr}^2}}{1 + \pi^2 \cdot \frac{B_s}{L_{cr}^2 \cdot G_c \cdot A_c}} \quad (1)$$

where:

- B_s Bending stiffness of the panel
- G_c Shear modulus of core material
- A_c Cross section of core material
- L_{cr} Buckling length

The related slenderness ratio $\bar{\lambda}$ is specified by taking into account the wrinkling stress σ_w according to equation (2).

$$\bar{\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_w \cdot (A_{F1} + A_{F2})}{N_{cr}}} \quad (2)$$

where: A_{F1} Cross section of face 1
 A_{F2} Cross section of face 2

3 BUCKLING TESTS ON SANDWICH PANELS

3.1 Test set up

Figure 2 shows the principle of the test setup. It consists of two retainingwalls, a hydraulic jack and two supports. The supports are realised by frictionless roller bearings so that the occurrence of restoring forces can be ruled out. These correspond to the recommendations from (10). The tests are carried out with horizontally installed specimens. Thus, the flexible positioning of the retaining wall does not restrict the length of the specimen. Furthermore, the design ruled out the possibility of the dead weight having an influence on the initial imperfection. The experimental setup simulates Euler case II and is therefore suited for investigating the global buckling of sandwich panels.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the principle of the test set up

Figure 3 shows the realised test set up. The upper left partial image shows the installation state of the test specimen before the start of the test. The details of both supports are presented in the two partial images below. The partial image on the right presents the axial view of the panel. Thereby, the specimen is unloaded in the alignment line (shown in red) between the two supports.

Fig. 3. a) Realised test set up b) support c) support at load introduction d) top view on the panel

3.2 Specimen

The test programme comprises experimental investigations of nine specimens. The test specimens have thicknesses of 60 mm, 80 mm and 100 mm and lengths between 3000 mm and 6000 mm. The buckling length of the test specimens refers to the centre of the supports (see Fig. 2). Therefore, the buckling length in each test is 507 mm longer than the actual panel length. An overview of the individual test specimens and the most important geometric characteristics is presented in Table 1. All test specimens are sandwich panels from one manufacturer, which have a PIR ridged foam core material.

Table 1. Geometric characteristics of the test specimens

Specimen	Thickness d_{SE} [mm]	Length L_{SE} [mm]	Buckling length L_{cr} [mm]
V01	100	6000	6507
V02	100	4500	5007
V03	80	6000	6507
V04	80	6000	6507
V05	80	5000	5507
V06	80	5000	5507
V07	80	3000	3507
V08	60	5000	5507
V09	60	5000	5507

3.3 Geometrical imperfections

Knowledge of the exact panel imperfections is essential in order to be able to determine the load bearing behaviour of axially loaded sandwich panels. For this purpose, the geometric imperfections of the specimen in the installed state were recorded before the start of the test. Therefore, a laser was used to create an alignment line between the two centres of the supports. This alignment line was used to determine the deviation of the centre point of the thickness of the panel from the ideal position at seven measuring points. The results of the measurements are shown in Figure 3. For all test specimens - with the exception of specimen V03 - the longitudinal curvature was aligned in such a way that the face of the panel, which was the top side in the production process, was on the concave side of the curvature. As expected, the imperfections increase with increasing slenderness of the test specimens. Thinner test specimens generally exhibit fewer geometric imperfections.

The maximum values of the determined geometric imperfections were considered for subsequent evaluation. Thereby, the maximum value of all specimen was below the limit value of $l/500$, which is the tolerance of the longitudinal curvature according to DIN EN 14509 (11) and is the imperfection approach of the new standard prEN 1993-7 (1).

Fig. 3. Overview of the measured geometrical imperfections

3.4 Test procedure

The tests were carried out displacement-controlled with a rate of 0.5 mm/min until the specimens failed. During the test, the lateral deflection of the test specimens was measured at five points over the buckling length. Thereby, the deformation was measured in the centre of the width of the panels and near the outer edge, so that a possible torsion of the test specimens could have been recorded. However, this was not observed in any of the tests, so that only a purely axial load on the sandwich panels occurred. The stresses in the faces were recorded using strain gauges. Thereby, two strain gauges were attached to each face in the centre of the buckling length. Laser displacement transducers were located in the area of the supports, which recorded the radial displacement of the roller bearings. This makes it possible to take the pure component displacement into account when analysing the tests.

Figure 4 shows the test progression of specimen V01 from the axial alignment perspective. The progression is representative for the entire test series. The left section shows the test specimen at a high load level shortly before the failure of the specimen. A sinusoidal deformation of the test specimen can be clearly recognised. The deflection is highest in the centre of the buckling length and decreases symmetrically towards both supports. The right-hand partial image shows the specimen after reaching the maximum load and the occurrence of component failure due to wrinkling of the face. The test specimen exhibited the typical load-bearing behaviour of the global buckling of sandwich panels according to the characteristics described in section 2.

Fig. 4. Procedure of a typical test

Figure 5 shows examples of wrinkling of the faces of three test specimens. The wrinkling occurs across the entire width of the panel and generally formed close to the centre of the buckling length. Due to the global geometric imperfections of the panel (Fig. 2) and the local structural and geometric imperfections, it was to be expected that the wrinkling would form around the centre of the buckling length, but not necessarily exactly on it.

Fig. 5. Example of wrinkling of the steel faces - typical failure mode of the panels

Figure 6 shows an example of the force-displacement diagram and the force-stress diagram of a typical test (V04). In both diagrams the analytical critical buckling load, according to equation (1), is indicated. The lateral deflection of the test specimen and the stresses in the faces remain low at low load levels. The deflection and the stress of the face increase significantly as the applied load approaches the critical buckling load. The failure of the test specimen then occurs due to the wrinkling of the face. The wrinkling stress can be determined by the measured value at the point of maximum load. To summarise, the test method and the load-deflection and load-stress relationship are consistent with the theoretical approach described in Section 2.

Fig. 6. Example of typical Load-Deflection- and Load-Stress-Curve

4 ANALYSIS OF TEST RESULTS

The so-called Southwell plot is used for the analysis of test results. It is a graphical method for determining the critical buckling load on the basis of experimentally determined load-deflection relationships. The derivation and a detailed description of this method can be found in (12). The method is based on the differential equation of a bar under axial centric loading with a sinusoidal affine eigenmode. The Southwell plot is suitable for determining the critical buckling load N_{cr} and an equivalent imperfection $e_{0,eq}$, which includes the geometrical as well as the structural imperfections. The critical buckling load determined in this way is to be regarded as an experimentally determined value and later helps to categorise the test results in buckling curves.

Figure 7 illustrates the procedure using the results of specimen V04 as an example. The evaluation of the initial ranges was deliberately omitted, as the behaviour of the specimen does not yet exhibit a clear affinity of the eigenmode. Furthermore interference ranges from the measurement signals, which inevitably occur with very small lateral deformations, should not be included in the calculation of the regression lines (13) (14) (15).

Fig. 7. Example of the Southwell plot of specimen V04

The comparison of the critical buckling load from the Southwell plot $N_{cr,sw}$ and the analytical approach $N_{cr,Engesser}$ (equation (1)) is shown in Figure 8. A very high level of agreement can be recognised. The deviation of the results from each other is generally less than $\pm 5\%$.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the analytically determined critical buckling loads with the results from the Southwell plot

Table 2 gives an overview of the test results. It provides the maximum value reached in each test and the critical buckling load determined analytically and by the Southwell plot. In addition, Table 2 compares the sizes of the imperfections determined using the Southwell plot and the measured imperfections from Fig. 3 along the buckling length. As expected, the equivalent imperfections provided by the Southwell plot are in general larger than the measured geometrical imperfections. The mean value of the imperfections of the Southwell plot is presented and serves as an imperfection approach for the derivation of the buckling curves.

Table 2. Overview of the results from the tests and the Southwell plot

Specimen	Loads			Imperfections	
	N_b [kN]	$N_{cr,Engesser}$ [kN]	$N_{cr,SW}$ [kN]	$e_{0,measured}/L_{cr}$ [-]	$e_{0,sw}/L_{cr}$ [-]
V01	87.2	98.9	103.3	1/4338.0	1/934.9
V02	118.1	143.9	147.7	1/1669.0	1/1203.6
V03	63.8	64.4	68.1	1/1084.5	~0
V04	60.1	64.4	65.6	1/929.6	1/1223
V05	71.2	82.3	82.6	1/2753.5	1/881.1
V06	70.8	82.3	84.6	1/1001.3	1/686.7
V07	114.5	149.4	153.2	1/734.2	1/595.9
V08	46.1	50.9	49.8	1/1223.7	1/1012.3
V09	40.9	50.9	46.2	1/1669.0	-
Mean value				1/1716.7	1/933.9

5 DERIVATION OF BUCKLING CURVES

The method according to Ayrton-Perry (16) is used to determine the buckling curves. This applies to the global buckling of a column with an eigenmode affine imperfection figure. The linear limit state of the cross-section can be formulated taking into account the equivalent imperfection value $e_{0,eq}$. This approach leads to the following solution of the reduction factor χ :

$$\chi = \frac{1}{\phi + \sqrt{\phi^2 - \bar{\lambda}^2}} \quad (3)$$

Where:

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{N_R}{M_{R,z}} \cdot e_{0,eq} + \bar{\lambda}^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

N_R and M_R are the resistance values of the column related to the respective axis with regard to the normal force and the moment:

$$N_R = \sigma_w \cdot (A_{F1} + A_{F2}) \quad (5)$$

$$M_R = \sigma_w \cdot e \cdot A_{Fi} \quad (6)$$

A more detailed description of this approach for sandwich panels can be found in (8).

The described experimental investigations and the results of the Southwell plot serve as the basis for the derivation of the buckling curves. Here, the equivalent imperfection value $e_{0,eq}$ is redefined for the sandwich panels of the test series presented and the following approach is chosen:

$$e_{0,eq} = e_{0,SW,mean\ value} \quad (7)$$

The mean value of the imperfections from the Southwell plot (Table 2) with the value $e_{0,SW,mean\ value} \approx 1/934$ in relation to the critical length of the sandwich panels is used as the equivalent imperfection.

The resulting buckling curves for the tested sandwich panels is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Buckling curves and experimental data

The investigations presented provide promising results. In the next step of the investigations, valid FEM results will be developed, which will serve as the basis for far-reaching parameter studies. On the basis of these studies, buckling curves will then be developed, taking into account safety theory. The aim is to enable the design of axially loaded sandwich panels with the aid of buckling stress lines in the future.

6 KNOWLEDGMENT

The test specimens for this series of tests were kindly provided by Fischer Profil GmbH. We would like to take this opportunity to thank the persons involved for their support and interest.

REFERENCES

1. **European Committee of Standardization.** *prEN 1993-7 (2024e) Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 7: Sandwich panels.* Brussels : s.n., 2024.
2. **Plantema, Frederik J.** *The bending and buckling of sandwich beams.* New York : Wiley, 1966.
3. **Stamm, Klaus und Witte, Horst.** *Sandwichkonstruktionen - Berechnung, Fertigung, Ausführung.* Wien, New York : Springer, 1974.
4. **Janczyk, Kevin und Kuhnhenne, Markus.** Numerical determination of the wrinkling stress of steel polyurethane sandwich panels. *8th International Symposium on Life-Cycle Civil Engineering, Milan.* 2023.
5. **Andrade, Pedro, et al.** On global and local buckling response of structural angle sandwich panels. *Thin-Walled Structures* . 2022, 180.
6. **Allen, H. G.** *Analysis and design of structural sandwich panels.* Oxford : Pergamon Press, 1969.
7. **Käpplein, Saskia und Thomas, Ummenhofer.** Axial beanspruchte Sandwichelemente in Rahmenlosen Konstruktionen. *Stahlbau.* 2010, 79.
8. **Janczyk, Kevin, et al.** Zum Biegeknicken von Sandwichelmenten. *Stahlbau* 92. 2023.
9. **Engesser, F.** Die Knickfestigkeit gerader Stäbe. *Zentralblatt der Bauverwaltung* 11. 1891.
10. **European Convention for Constructional Steelwork (ECCS)** . *Manual on stability of steel structures, ECCS Technical Committee 8 – structural stability.* 1984.
11. **DIN German Institute for Standardization.** *Self-supporting double skin metal faced insulating panels - Factory made products - Specifications; German version EN 14509:2013.* Berlin : s.n., 2013.
12. **Southwell, R.V.** On the analysis of experimental observations in problems of elastic stability. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character.* 1932.
13. **Nonn, Jonas, Wolters, Kevin und Feldmann, Markus.** Universelle Hochleistungsstützen aus hochfesten Stählen ohne Schweißen. *Stahlbau.* 2023.
14. **Nonn, Jonas und Feldmann, Markus.** Imperfections of LTB tests with directionally true loading using the extended Southwell-method. *Eurosteel 2021, Sheffield.* 2021.
15. **Nonn, Jonas, et al.** Experimental investigations on composite columns: round hollow sections with embedded solid core section made of high strength steel. *Eurosteel 2023, Amsterdam.* 2023.
16. **Perry, J. und Ayrton, W.** On Struts. *The Engineer.* 1886.